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AN OVERVIEW ON NEWER ANTIDIABETIC AGENTS

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ABSTRACT

Diabetes mellitus is a group of metabolic diseases characterized by chronic hyperglycemia resulting from defects in insulin secretion, insulin action. Different classes of diabetes mellitus type1, type2 ,gestational is summarized. It is predicted that the prevalence of DM in adults of which type2 is becoming prominent mostly in developing countries. The treatment strategies are listed and many new drugs are currently in development for treatment of diabetes including more products with new mechanisms .Drugs with application submitted for US food and Drug administration (FDA) approval and drugs currently in phase3 clinical trials are summarized.

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INTRODUCTION**DEFINITION**

Diabetes mellitus is a group of metabolic diseases characterized by chronic hyperglycemia resulting from defects in insulin secretion, insulin action, or both. Metabolic abnormalities in carbohydrates, lipids, and proteins result from the importance of insulin as an anabolic hormone. Low levels of insulin to achieve adequate response and/or insulin resistance of target tissues, mainly skeletal muscles, adipose tissue, and to a lesser extent, liver, at the level of insulin receptors, signal transduction system, and/or effector enzymes or genes are responsible for these metabolic abnormalities. The severity of symptoms is due to the type and duration of diabetes. Some of the diabetes patients are asymptomatic especially those with type 2 diabetes during the early years of the disease, others with marked hyperglycemia and especially in children with absolute insulin deficiency may suffer from polyuria, polydipsia, polyphagia, weight loss, and blurred vision. Uncontrolled diabetes may lead to stupor, coma and if not treated death, due to ketoacidosis or rare from nonketotic hyperosmolar syndrome¹⁻³.

Classification of Diabetes :

Type 1 diabetes encompasses diabetes that is a result of pancreatic beta cell destruction and is prone to ketoacidosis. This form includes cases due to an autoimmune process and those for which the etiology of beta cell destruction is unknown.

Type 2 diabetes may range from predominant insulin resistance with relative insulin deficiency to a predominant secretory defect with insulin resistance.

Gestational diabetes mellitus refers to glucose intolerance with onset or first recognition during pregnancy.

Other specific types include a wide variety of relatively uncommon conditions, primarily specific genetically defined forms of diabetes or diabetes associated with other diseases or drug use⁴.

Includes latent autoimmune diabetes in adults (LADA); the term used to describe the small number of people with apparent type 2 diabetes who appear to have immune-mediated loss of pancreatic beta cells⁵.

Epidemiology :

It is estimated that 366 million people had DM in 2011; by 2030 this would have risen to 552 million⁶. The number of people with type 2 DM is increasing in every country with 80% of people with DM living in low- and middle-income countries. DM caused 4.6 million deaths in 2011⁸. It is estimated that 439 million people would have type 2 DM by the year 2030⁷. The incidence of type 2 DM varies substantially from one geographical region to the other as a result of environmental and lifestyle risk factors⁸. Literature search has shown that there are few data available on the prevalence of type 2 DM in Africa as a whole. Studies examining data trends within Africa point to evidence of a dramatic increase in prevalence in both rural and urban setting, and affecting both gender equally⁹. The majority of the DM burden in Africa appears to be type 2 DM, with less than 10% of DM cases being type 1 DM¹⁰⁻¹¹. Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) report estimates that DM affects about 25.8 million people in the US (7.8% of the population) in 2010 with 90% to 95% of them being type 2 DM¹². It is predicted that the prevalence of DM in adults of which type 2 DM is becoming prominent will increase in the next two decades and much of the increase will occur in developing countries where the majority of patients are aged between 45 and 64 years¹³. It is projected that the latter will equal or even exceed the former in developing nations, thus culminating in a double burden as a result of the current trend of transition from communicable to non-communicable diseases¹⁴.

TREATMENT STRATEGIES :**ORAL****INSULIN****ORAL⁹ :**

These are the OAD'S which have been in clinical research for good number of years and for which considerable research, clinical experience and safety data are available.

SULFONYL UREAS :

Glibenclimide

Glipizide

Gliclazide

Glimepiride

BIGUANIDES:

Metformin

THIAZOLIDINEDIONE:

Pioglitazone

ALPHA_GLUCOSIDASE INHIBITORS :

Agarose

Voglibose

MEGLITINIDE ANALOGES :

Repaglinide

Nateglinide

INSULIN :

Insulin is supplied conventionally through subcutaneous route. In the early days, impurities present in bovine insulin led to many immunological reactions. As a result of the advancements such as recombinant DNA technology, more purified forms of insulin is available today¹⁰.

INSULIN INHALERS

It is a non-invasive, well tolerated delivery system which is effective for both type 1 and type 2 diabetes mellitus. The glycemic control by this method is comparable to subcutaneous route and it also enhances patient satisfaction, quality of life and acceptance for Intense Insulin Therapy in a diabetic patient¹¹. The aerosolized insulin has a diameter of about 3 μ m which enhances the alveolar disposition and low oropharyngeal and large airway disposition. The onset of action following systemic absorption is about 20 minutes, which is rapid. The action lasts for about 6-8 hours, which is comparable to that in subcutaneous administration. Exuberant was the first inhaled insulin preparation available. It was delivered with an aerosol device called exuberant inhaler. Nebulizers, metered dose inhalers and aqueous mist inhalers are being investigated. Inhalation is an excellent mode for delivering pre-meal time insulin. It can be used for delivering fast acting insulin only. It is less effective in smokers and those with pulmonary diseases. The incidence of hypoglycemia is also increased with this route.^{11,12}

BUCCAL DELIVERY OF INSULIN

Mucosal membranes of the inner lining of cheeks can act as excellent sites for insulin delivery. The area is robust, rich in blood supply, has expansive smooth muscle and provides short cellular recovery following damage or injury^{12,13}. Visibility and accessibility of buccal mucosa also makes it an ideal site for delivery. The insulin sprayed into buccal mucosa cannot enter deep lungs because of its size and hence it is safe for lungs¹³. Insulin which is administered through buccal route is called buccal insulin, when it reaches the systemic circulation.¹ The main disadvantage of this route is the lower bioavailability due to the relatively low passage of active agent across the mucosal epithelium. Bio adhesive polymers can be used as an alternative. They adhere to the biological substrate to provide continued contact of the agent with the site of delivery. The various bio adhesive formulations include gels, films, tablets, vesicles, nanoparticles and sponges. They are retained for longer time and hence show improved pharmacokinetic as well as absorption properties. Gels, transferosomes, pelleted nanoparticles, tablets, patches, films, sponges, sprays etc. are the currently available buccal delivery formulations.^{12,13}

PULMONARY DELIVERY OF INSULIN

Insulin can be administered by pulmonary route using two techniques - aerosol inhalation and intratracheal instillation. Aerosol offers more uniform distribution with greater extent of penetration into peripheral or into alveolar region of the lungs. When delivered into the lungs, they are readily absorbed through the alveolar region directly into blood circulation. This can be achieved by liquid nebulizers, aerosol based metered dose inhalers and dry powder dispersion devices. Simplicity of self administration, large surface area of lungs that improves absorption, relatively high bioavailability and non-invasiveness are the advantages of this delivery system.¹⁴

ORAL DELIVERY OF INSULIN

An oral dosage form is the preferred form of delivery because of the ease of administration, patient compliance and economical issues. No oral preparations of insulin are available till date. The advantage of this route of insulin delivery is the capability of insulin to mimic normal physiological role. Thus it can become more efficacious in glucose homeostasis.¹⁵ The difficulties encountered in the oral delivery of insulin include degradation of the protein at lower pH of stomach and by different digestive enzymes in stomach and small intestine. This causes a decrease in bioavailability as low as $\leq 0.5\%$.^{14,15} The variation in permeability across GIT for insulin and stability issues of the dosage form are the other major challenges for oral insulin delivery¹⁶. Several gastrointestinal patch systems are available today and they provide bio adhesion, unidirectional release and protection for the drug from pH variations and also from enzymes. This combination of functions improves bioavailability of large sized molecules.² Protection of insulin from gastric environment has been achieved by coating the nanoparticles with pH sensitive polymers, which will dissolve in the mildly acidic environment of the intestine.^{17,18} Complexation hydrogels significantly enhance oral absorption of insulin with notable hypoglycaemic effect.¹⁹ Recombinant human insulin can be delivered by using niosomal formulations.²⁰⁻²¹

TRANSDERMAL DELIVERY OF INSULIN

It is a needle free technique, which is convenient with good patient compliance and prolonged therapeutic application. It bypasses first pass metabolism and escapes degradation by gastric enzymes. Iontophoresis is a technique that improves the transdermal delivery of compounds through skin by application of a small amount of electrical current. Microdermabrasion is another method that improves the permeability of insulin through skin. It is achieved by mildly damaging or removing the outer layer of skin, stratum corneum.²²⁻²³

INSULIN DEVICES

Insulin infusion devices may be classified as open loop and closed-loop systems. Programmable open-loop micro pump insulin delivery device consists of a small, lightweight, portable insulin micro pump and plastic tubing which connects the pump to a needle inserted under the skin. Insulin release patterns in them can be preprogrammed and initiated by timer or by the diabetic patient himself. This device demands a very careful monitoring of blood glucose level. Also the patients using these devices were reported to show high incidence of ketoacidosis. Implantable versions of open loop insulin infusion devices were also introduced. Chemically controlled closed loop insulin delivery devices work by feedback mechanism. It is an effective alternative in the absence of an effective pancreas or β -cell transplantation. It mimics pancreatic activity. They are biocompatible and non-toxic. The bio hybrid artificial pancreas is another type of insulin diffusion device, which is under research. These contain β -cells enclosed within a semi permeable membrane, which is biocompatible. The semi permeable membrane is permeable to glucose and insulin. Special has to be given to exclude immune cells in order to prevent rejection by the body.²⁴⁻²⁶

INSULIN DELIVERY USING PEN DEVICES

It is a convenient and accurate method of insulin delivery. Its goal is to improve glycaemic control by making it less difficult to follow the current recommendations for intensive insulin regimens. Two types of pens are available; prefilled and reusable. Pens are available in various styles. Insulin pens have the potential to become a major asset for the improved compliance among all patients undergoing insulin therapy.

OTHER NOVEL METHODS IN INSULIN DELIVERY

Erythrocytes, which are the most abundant cells in the body, can be used as effective carriers of many different drugs including insulin. Biocompatibility, biodegradability, long circulation half life and the ability to get loaded with a variety of chemically and biologically active compounds make resealed erythrocytes excellent carriers of therapeutic agents²⁷. Dendrimers are macromolecules with highly branched 3D structure²⁸. They also are used for successful delivery of insulin.

NEWER ORAL ANTIDIABETIC AGENTS:

DIPEPTIDYL PEPTIDASE 4 (DPP-4) INHIBITORS:

The DPP-4 inhibitors are incretin enhancers. DPP-4 inhibitors are thought to work by slowing the inactivation of the incretin hormones glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) and glucosedependentinsulinotropic peptide. These agents are released by the gastrointestinal tract in response to food and are involved with the stimulation of glucose-dependent insulin secretion. By inhibiting their inactivation, these drugs prolong the effects of these incretin hormones. The DPP-4 inhibitors have been assessed as monotherapy and in conjunction with insulin, metformin, sulfonylureas, and thiazolidinedione's in patients with type 2 diabetes. Although the DPP-4 inhibitors have been shown to improve glycemic control, as with most other new agents used in the treatment of diabetes, data have not been published addressing the effects of the DPP-4 inhibitors on key outcome measures such as mortality, diabetes complications, or health related quality of life.²⁹

Alogliptin

Alogliptin is a highly selective inhibitor of DPP-4, demonstrating > 10,000 times more selectivity for DPP-4 than for other related proteases. After oral administration of alogliptin in a range of doses from 25 to 800 mg.

Mechanism of Action

Alogliptin is capable of decreasing the average A1C level in patients with type 2 diabetes when used alone or in combination with insulin, metformin, a sulfonylurea, or a thiazolidinedione.³⁰

Adverse reactions reported have also included nasopharyngitis, headache, and upper respiratory tract infection. Alogliptin appears to have a neutral effect on weight and lipids.³¹⁻³⁴

Dutogliptin

Dutogliptin is also an oral DPP-4 inhibitor under evaluation for once daily dosing in patients with type 2 diabetes. To date, it has demonstrated activity in a short-term study when administered once daily in conjunction with metformin or metformin plus a thiazolidinedione; participants are now being recruited for a phase 3 study.

Linagliptin

Linagliptin is another oral DPP-4 inhibitor under evaluation for once daily dosing in patients with type 2 Diabetes. To date, it has demonstrated activity in a short-term study when administered once daily in patients with type 2 diabetes; recruitment is ongoing for a number of phase 3 studies assessing linagliptin as mono-therapy and in combination with pioglitazone, metformin, or metformin plus a sulfonylurea.

Saxagliptin

Saxagliptin is capable of decreasing the average A1C level in patients with type 2 diabetes when used alone or in combination with metformin, a sulfonylurea, or a thiazolidinedione. Treatment with saxagliptin alone has been weight neutral. Common adverse reactions reported in the clinical trials with saxagliptin include nasopharyngitis, headache, diarrhea, upper respiratory infections, influenza, and urinary tract infection.

Vildagliptin

Vildagliptin alone or in combination with metformin, a thiazolidinedione, or insulin is capable of decreasing fasting plasma glucose levels and improving A1C levels in patients with type 2 diabetes. Adverse reactions reported in the clinical trials have generally been similar to those reported with placebo and have included cough, nasopharyngitis, headache, hypoglycemia, dizziness, dyspepsia, nausea, constipation, and diarrhea. Vildagliptin had no impact on patient weight in the majority of studies.

Glucagon-LIKE PEPTIDE 1 (GLP-1) ANALOGS

The GLP-1 analogs induce their activity through a glucose-dependent stimulation of insulin secretion, inhibition of glucagon secretion, slowing of gastric emptying, and reduction in appetite.

AVE0010/ZP-10

Limited clinical data are available for AVE0010. A1C was reduced 0.28% to 0.69% compared to placebo in a range of doses from 5 mg once daily to 30 mg twice daily administered subcutaneously. Efficacy was similar with once-daily and twice-daily regimens. Greater weight loss with AVE0010 than with placebo was observed at doses of 20 and 30 mg once daily and 30 mg twice daily. Nausea and vomiting were the most common adverse effects. Recruitment is ongoing for a number of phase 3 studies evaluating AVE0010 as monotherapy and in addition to basal insulin, metformin, a sulfonylurea, or pioglitazone in patients with type 2 diabetes, as well as a study comparing AVE0010 and exenatide in association with metformin in patients with type 2 diabetes.

Exenatide LAR

The slow-release or long-acting release (LAR) formulation of exenatide is in phase 3 development. It is intended for once-weekly subcutaneous administration for the treatment of type 2 diabetes.

Liraglutide

Liraglutide is under evaluation for use in the treatment of patients with type 2 diabetes as an adjunct to diet and exercise, either as monotherapy or in combination with commonly used diabetes medications, including sulfonylureas and metformin. In clinical trials, Liraglutide has been associated with a reduction in A1C and fasting plasma glucose with either weight loss or no change in body weight. Significant reductions in A1C have been observed at doses of 0.1–2 mg administered subcutaneously once daily. Adverse effects associated with Liraglutide therapy have included headache, dizziness, nausea, and vomiting.

LY2189265

Results of studies with LY2189265 have not been published. Recruitment is currently ongoing for a phase 2/3 study comparing LY2189265 with sitagliptin in patients with type 2 diabetes on metformin.

Taspoglutide

Taspoglutide administered subcutaneously once weekly has been associated with reductions in fasting blood glucose, improvement in A1C, and weight loss when added to metformin therapy in patients with type 2 diabetes in short-term studies. Recruitment is ongoing for studies assessing taspoglutide as initial monotherapy and in conjunction with metformin, metformin plus pioglitazone, metformin plus a sulfonylurea, or metformin plus a thiazolidinedione. In several of these studies, Taspoglutide is being compared head-to-head with exenatide, insulin glargine, and sitagliptin.

PEROXISOME PROLIFERATOR-ACTIVATED RECEPTOR (PPAR) AGONISTS

The PPAR- γ agonists act as insulin sensitizers, reducing fasting glucose and A1C. The thiazolidinediones were the first class of PPAR- γ agonists to be approved for use in diabetes. Balaglitazone and rivoglitazone are thiazolidinediones in phase 3 studies in patients with type 2 diabetes. The partial PPAR- γ agonists, also known as Selective PPAR Modulators (SPPARMs), have been developed in an attempt to minimize the side effects of the full agonists while maintaining the therapeutic effect. Insufficient data are available at this time to determine if the selective PPAR modulators will have fewer adverse effects.

Balaglitazone

Balaglitazone is a selective partial PPAR- γ agonist. It has been suggested that partial PPAR- γ agonists may have a favorable adverse effect profile relative to the full PPAR- γ agonists pioglitazone and rosiglitazone. However, results of clinical studies directly comparing these agents are not yet available. A phase 3 study assessing the efficacy and safety of balaglitazone compared to pioglitazone in patients with type 2 diabetes receiving stable insulin therapy is currently enrolling patients.

Rivoglitazone

Rivoglitazone is a potent PPAR- γ agonist currently under evaluation in a phase 3 study comparing it to Placebo and pioglitazone in patients with type 2 diabetes not adequately controlled with diet and exercise or with no thiazolidinedione antihyperglycemic monotherapy. In an earlier open-label comparative 6-week study, rivoglitazone 2-mg and 5-mg doses once daily were associated with greater reductions in fasting plasma glucose than pioglitazone 30 mg; however, these rivoglitazone doses were also associated with a greater incidence of peripheral edema and weight gain.

SELECTIVE SODIUM GLUCOSE COTRANSPORTER 2 INHIBITORS

The selective sodium glucose cotransporter 2 inhibitors are a new class of agents. The sodium glucose cotransporter type 2 (SGLT2) located in the plasma membrane of cells lining the proximal tubule mediates the majority of renal glucose reabsorption from the tubular fluid. Blood glucose is continuously filtered by the renal glomeruli and then reabsorbed in the renal proximal tubules by SGLT2, and to a lesser extent SGLT1, preventing the loss of glucose in the urine. Competitive inhibitors of SGLT2 provoke renal excretion of glucose; potentially lowering elevated blood glucose levels in patients with diabetes. These agents are expected to improve plasma glucose levels and decrease body weight in patients with type 2 diabetes without causing hypoglycemia.

Dapagliflozin

Dapagliflozin is in the early portion of phase 3 development for use as a monotherapy agent or in combination with other oral hypoglycemic agents. The drug has been well tolerated in early clinical studies with the most common adverse reactions being urinary tract infection, dizziness, headache, fatigue, back pain, and nasopharyngitis. It is in the early portion of phase 3 development for use as a monotherapy agent or in combination with other oral hypoglycemic agents. The drug has been well tolerated in early clinical studies with the most common adverse reactions being urinary tract infection, dizziness, headache, fatigue, back pain, and nasopharyngitis.

Dapagliflozin is currently under evaluation in a number of phase 3 studies assessing the agent as monotherapy in patients with type 2 diabetes not adequately controlled with diet and exercise, as well as studies assessing Dapagliflozin in conjunction with metformin, a sulfonylurea, a thiazolidinedione, or insulin.

GLINIDES

The glinides, including Nateglinide, repaglinide, and mitiglinide, are agents that enhance mealtime insulin secretion and reduce postprandial hyperglycemia. Nateglinide and repaglinide have been available in the United States since 2000 and 1997, respectively.

Mitiglinide

Mitiglinide has been available in Japan since 2004 and is currently in phase 3 studies in the United States. It has been reported to have a more β -cell-selective effect on the adenosine triphosphate-dependent potassium channels than Nateglinide and repaglinide and to have no active metabolites or cytochrome P450 drug interactions. Several recently published studies conducted in Japan have assessed premeal mitiglinide combined with once-daily insulin and twice-daily premixed insulin.⁴⁶

INSULINS

Rapid acting insulin

These insulin analogs have a more rapid onset of action (15-30 min) and shorter activity duration (4 to 5 h). Their peak action ranges from 30-90 min post injection. By a single or two amino acid alterations in the insulin molecule, the ability to associate into hexamers is reduced such that they are readily absorbed, however, these modifications do not change the biological properties of these analogs. Examples of rapid acting insulin include Lispro and Aspart. In Insulin Lispro (LysB28, ProB29), the positions of proline at position B28 and lysine at position B29 in the B chain have been reversed. In insulin Aspart, the proline at position 28 has been replaced by aspartic acid.⁷⁵ These rapid acting analogs can be used at mealtime to achieve optimum level of insulin for utilization of glucose released after eating.⁴⁷

Short acting insulin

Short acting insulin analogs have an onset of action of around 0.5-1 h, peak action of 2-4 h and activity duration of 6-8 h. Examples of these preparations include Actrapid, Humulin, Hypurin and Neutral. These insulin analogs should be injected into the body 20-30 min before meal so as to get optimum insulin activity for carbohydrate metabolism.

Intermediate acting insulin

Intermediate acting insulin analogs have an onset of action around 1-2 h, peak action of 6-10 h and activity duration of 10-16 h. Examples of intermediate acting insulin include NPH (Neutral Protamine Hagedorn) and LENTE (from the Latin "lentus," meaning slow, or sluggish) insulin. The absorption rate of NPH insulin is reduced by the addition of protamine to the insulin preparation. In insulin LENTE, the same is achieved by the addition of zinc to the insulin preparation.

Long acting insulin

These insulin analogs have an onset of action around 2 h, peak action (sometimes no peak action) of 6 h and activity duration of up to 36 h. One way to prolong insulin activity is designing analogs with more positively charged amino acids so as to raise the isoelectric point of insulin to near neutral pH.⁷⁷ This helps in reducing the solubility of insulin at neutral pH after injection into the body and the absorption into the blood stream will be delayed. Some of the long acting insulin preparations also have protamine or zinc added to them to increase absorption time. Insulin detemir, also called desB30 insulin, is an example of long acting insulin. In insulin detemir, the threonine at position B30 in the B chain is removed and a 14-C fatty acid i.e. myristic acid is attached to the lysine at position B29 in the B chain. Attachment of myristic acid helps in insulin hexamer formation and increases the binding of insulin to plasma albumin which delays the free insulin release and which prolongs the activity of insulin.⁴⁸⁻⁴⁹

NEWER INSULIN ANALOGUE

A variety of insulin formulations are currently in development including inhaled formulations, intranasal formulations, oral formulations, and injectable analogs.

Inhaled Technosphere Insulin

Inhaled Technosphere insulin is inhaled insulin in development for administration using a palm-sized handheld breath-activated inhaler. The Technosphere particles are composed of human regular insulin loaded into a diketopiperazine molecule. The particles dissolve rapidly at physiological pH, providing for rapid insulin absorption from the lungs. Technosphere insulin is absorbed within 15 minutes, has an onset of action of ~ 25–30 minutes, and has duration of action of ~ 2–3 hours.

Oral Insulin Spray

An oral insulin spray in development by Genex Biotechnology is in phase 3 studies in the United States but has already been approved in Ecuador and India. The insulin is absorbed buccally following administration with a proprietary RapidMist device that resembles the metered-dose inhalers used in the treatment of asthma. The formulation is tasteless and odorless.

Rapid-Acting Insulin for Injection (VIAject)

VIAject is a novel ultra-fast insulin formulation composed of human soluble insulin and ingredients designed to increase the rate of absorption (EDTA and citric acid). These ingredients pull the zinc ions away from human insulin hexamers and mask charges on the surface of the insulin molecule, causing the insulin hexamers to dissociate and preventing re-association to the hexameric state with subcutaneous administration. VIAject has exhibited a quicker onset of action than insulin lispro and human soluble insulin (time to early half-maximal activity 33 minutes with VIAject vs. 85 minutes with insulin lispro and 66 minutes with human soluble insulin; $P < 0.05$). When administered immediately before a meal, VIAject was associated with improved post-prandial blood glucose control, reduced hyperglycemia in the first 3 hours after a meal, and reduced hypoglycemia through 8 hours compared to regular human insulin. Phase 3 studies comparing insulin VIAject and regular human insulin in patients with type 1 and type 2 diabetes have recently been completed.

Other AGENTS

A wide variety of other agents are also in development for the treatment of type 1 or type 2 diabetes.

Bromocriptine

Bromocriptine is a dopamine D2 receptor agonist that is approved for the treatment of dysfunctions associated with hyperprolactinemia, acromegaly, and Parkinson's disease and has been in development for the treatment of type 2 diabetes for several years. A new drug application for a quick-release formulation was granted approvable status by the FDA in 2006. However, at least one additional safety study was necessary before the drug could be approved.

Otelixizumab

Otelixizumab is a humanized anti-CD3 monoclonal antibody currently being evaluated in clinical studies in patients with new-onset type 1 diabetes. Otelixizumab binds to the CD3/TCR complex and blocks full T-cell activation, proliferation, and cytokine release. It has been hypothesized that otelixizumab's downregulation of T effector cells via binding of the T-cell receptors will result in inhibition of the autoimmune attack on β -cells in the pancreatic islets and establishment of longlasting operational tolerance by the generation and expansion of regulatory T-cells, which prevent further autoimmune destruction. A phase 3 study is currently underway assessing whether an 8-day series of otelixizumab infusions will lead to greater improvement in insulin secretion than placebo in adults 18–35 years of age with new-onset type 1 diabetes.

Recombinant Human Glutamic Acid Decarboxylase-65 (rhGAD65)

RhGAD65 is a vaccine that induces immunotolerization and may thereby slow or prevent autoimmune destruction of pancreatic islet cells. Antibodies against GAD are present at the time of diagnosis in 80–90% of patients with type 1 diabetes. In patients with adult-onset autoimmune diabetes and the presence of antibodies against GAD, administration of rhGAD65 has been associated with reduced A1C and increased fasting and stimulated C-peptide levels for 2 years. Two phase 3 studies were recently initiated to assess whether rhGAD65 formulated in alum preserves the body's own insulin-producing capacity in patients recently diagnosed with type 1 diabetes. One study will enroll subjects 10–20 years of age; the other will enroll subjects 8–45 years of age. Results will not be available for several years.

Succinobucol

Succinobucol is an oral antioxidant lipid peroxidation inhibitor and vascular cell adhesion molecule antagonist that are in phase 3 development for the treatment of atherosclerosis and type 2 diabetes. It is a monosuccinate ester of probucol, a previously approved lipid-lowering agent.

Teplizumab

Teplizumab is a humanized anti-CD3 monoclonal antibody. Like otelexi-zumab, teplizumab is hypothesized to minimize cytokine release and pre-vent the progressive destruction of β -cells. 136A phase 3 study is currently evaluating the effects of 14 days of intravenous teplizumab in patients 8–35 years of age with new-onset type 1 diabetes, followed by retreatment at 6 months. The primary study endpoint is a successful clinical response as assessed by subjects' total daily insulin usage and A1C at 1 year.⁵⁰

ROLE OF PHARMACIST IN COUNSELLING DIABETES MELLITUS:

The pharmacist can educate the patients about the proper use of medication, screening for drug interactions, explain monitoring devices, and make recommendations for ancillary products and services. The pharmacist can monitor the patient's blood glucose levels and keep a track of it. During their contact, the patients can ask the pharmacist any questions they did not ask the physicians and can get further information regarding diabetes. The pharmacist can also counsel the patients regarding insulin administration regularly so that the onset of complications can be postponed by having tight glycemic control. Another important role of pharmacist is always being available to answer the questions of the patients. Overall, it is the pharmacist's role to help a diabetic patient in the best possible way to cope with their disease.²¹

Essential components of diabetic counseling

Since diabetes is a chronic complication affecting the diabetic patient at various levels, the counseling should focus on the nature of the disease, lifestyle modifications, medications, and acute and chronic complications.

I. Counseling regarding the disease: The diabetic patients should be explained that the disease is lifelong, progressive and needs necessary modifications in the lifestyle pattern. They should also stress upon the importance of pharmacotherapy, especially the need for strict compliance with the prescribed medication. The patients should be also explained that the disease may affect the quality of life if not well controlled.

II. Counseling regarding lifestyle modifications: While counseling regarding the life style modifications, the pharmacist should focus on the key areas including diet, exercise, smoking and alcohol intake.

A. Diet: Dietary control is the mainstay of treatment in type 2 diabetes and an integral part in type 1 diabetes. Among the dietary counseling, importance should be given for the dietary content including carbohydrate, fat and fiber intake.

1. Carbohydrates: The blood glucose level is closely affected by the carbohydrate intake. Daily intake should be kept fairly constant and the amount given should be appropriate to the level of physical activity. Most young people will require 180 g of carbohydrate per day, whereas 100 g may suffice for an elderly patient. If fiber rich food such as whole meal bread, jacket potatoes, etc. are eaten, then the carbohydrate content of the diet make up to 50% to 55% of the calories. People with diabetes should limit their sugar intake, but total exclusion of sugar from the diet is impractical and unnecessary.

2. Fat: Since there is an increased risk of death from coronary artery disease in diabetics, it is wise to restrict saturated fats and to substitute them with unsaturated fats. Furthermore, obesity is a major problem in diabetes, and fats contain more than twice the energy content per unit weight than either carbohydrate or proteins. More severe restrictions may be indicated for individuals with hypercholesterolemia.

3. Fiber: Dietary fiber has two useful properties. Firstly it is physically bulky and increases satiety. Secondly, fiber delays the digestion and absorption of complex carbohydrates, thereby minimizing hyperglycemia. For an average person with NIDDM, 15gm of soluble fiber (from fruits, pulses and vegetables) is likely to produce a 10% improvement in fasting blood glucose, glycated hemoglobin and low-density lipoprotein cholesterol.²¹

B. Exercise and physical activity: Exercise can help to promote weight loss and maintain ideal body weight when combined with restricted caloric intake. In type 1 diabetes, care must be taken to have adequate metabolic control prior to exercise and to monitor blood glucose before and after exercise. Exercise is not recommended if the patient has poorly controlled labile blood glucose level or is at increased risk of diabetic complications.

C. Alcohol intake: Even if the blood glucose of the patient is well controlled, modest amount of alcohol will significantly alter blood glucose levels. In general, the same guidelines of alcohol use applicable to the general public apply to patients with diabetes.²¹

D. Smoking: People with diabetes, especially those over age 40 years, who smoke and have high blood pressure and cholesterol, are at a higher risk for cardiovascular problems. When the large blood vessels (arteries) are blocked, heart attack and stroke often result. This hardening or blockage may also occur in the small arteries that supply blood to the legs and feet. Smoking can also lead to serious complications like infections, ulcers, gangrene, and even amputations.

III. Counseling regarding medications: Though lifestyle modifications play an important role in diabetes management, it is well established by landmark studies that the chronic complications can be prevented by strict glycemic control. Hence, the pharmacist has an immense role in counseling diabetic patients regarding the drugs. Counseling should be emphasized for oral anti diabetic agents as well as for insulin.

1. Oral hypoglycemic agents (OHAs): If the patient is diagnosed with Type 2 diabetes, he/ she is more likely to be prescribed OHAs. Some of the commonly prescribed oral hypoglycemic agents and the important counseling points are discussed below.

Some general principles to be followed for patients on OHAs:

The patient should be cautioned not to skip meals at any time and to follow regular eating patterns to prevent hypoglycemia. OHAs are comparatively safe drugs. However some patients may develop loss of appetite, nausea and vomiting, abdominal pain, cramps, malaise, diarrhea or weight loss.

1. Insulin: All patients with type 1 diabetes require insulin. Some patients with type 2 diabetes who initially respond to dietary modification and/ or oral anti diabetic medications eventually require insulin therapy. There are a wide variety of insulin preparations available now. These may differ in source, onset of action, time to peak effect, and duration of action. The clinician will prescribe the type of insulin which suits an individual best.

CONCLUSION

Diabetes mellitus is the outbreak of the century and without effective diagnostic procedures at an early stage, diabetes will rise unstoppably. This review focuses on diabetes and newer classes of drugs which are available. As the prevalence of diabetes is increasing at an alarming rate, more approaches are to be focused towards the early diagnosis and prevention of the disease. There is a need for the development of newer classes of drugs to show more precise action of drug at molecular level on the human body.

ABBREVIATION:

FDA : Food and Drug administration
 DM : Diabetes mellitus
 LADA : Latent autoimmune diabetes in adults
 CDC : Centre for disease control and prevention
 DPP_4 : Dipeptidyl peptidase 4
 GLP : Glucagon like peptide
 LAR : Long acting release
 PPAR : Peroxisomes proliferatoractivated receptor
 SGLT2 : Sodium glucose co-transporter type2
 EDTA : Ethylene diamine tetraacetic acid
 RHGAD65: Recombinant human glutamic acid decarboxylase 65

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